

Lithium Air Batteries

Students from NTU-RPI-DTU Innovation workshop

ABSTACT

Lithium air batteries are one of the most promising battery systems for transport applications, but also an challenging system to create. This project aims at studying the processes involving Lithium peroxide on carbon electrodes. One aspect is to find novel ways to image the process to improve our understanding of them.